

High-resolution species distribution modelling to guide eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) management

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ABSTRACT

Eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) meadows are declining globally despite their critical role as foundational ecosystems and water quality indicators, e.g. under the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD). With the EU Nature Restoration Regulation mandating recovery targets, robust habitat distribution maps are urgently needed to support evidence-based restoration. Traditional surveys provide detailed local estimates but lack the spatial coverage required for comprehensive mapping.

We developed a high-resolution (50 × 50 m) species distribution model (SDM) for *Z. marina* across Denmark's ~7000 km coastline using comprehensive national monitoring data (NOVANA, 2011–2022). A Random Forest model trained on ~30,000 field observations and validated on 7500 independent samples achieved strong predictive performance (accuracy: 80.3%, 95% CI: 79.4–81.2%), estimating current coverage at ~2000 km².

Critically, the model moves beyond traditional habitat suitability mapping to also predict depth distribution limits (Zmax), achieving strong agreement with independent WFD field observations of Zmax for 85 of 109 water bodies ($r = 0.779$, slope = 0.99, mean error <1 m). This accuracy provides actionable restoration targets aligned with EU mandates.

Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) analysis identified light availability at depth (Iz) as the most influential predictor (ALE range = 0.83), followed by Maximum Exposure Index (MEI, 0.70) and 95th percentile temperature (T95, 0.68), all showing nonlinear relationships with eelgrass presence.

Beyond mapping current distribution, the model enables scenario-based assessments of restoration feasibility under improved water clarity and climate change. The methodology is scalable to other species and regions, offering a robust framework for adaptive management and supporting EU restoration goals.

1. Introduction

Eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) is a foundational macrophyte species widely distributed in shallow coastal ecosystems throughout the Northern Hemisphere and is the most widespread of the world's ~60 seagrass species (Den Hartog, 1970; Green and Short, 2003). These extensive meadows provide essential ecological functions including biodiversity support, and nursery grounds for commercially important species, coastal protection, carbon and nutrient retention (do Amaral et al., 2023). Due to its key ecological functions and predictable response to environmental changes, extended eelgrass meadows reflect healthy coastal ecosystems eelgrass and is a key indicator species for marine water quality under the European Water Framework Directive (WFD),

where e.g. its depth limit is one of the indicators for the ecological status of coastal waters (Krause-Jensen et al., 2005; Marbà et al., 2013).

Despite their well-established ecological and economic values, seagrasses including *Z. marina* are declining at European and global scales (de Los Santos et al., 2019; Waycott et al., 2009). Threats include eutrophication, mechanical impacts, climate-induced warming, disease outbreaks, and various other stressors (de Los Santos et al., 2019). The widespread losses of eelgrass along with many other species and habitats have spurred protection and restoration efforts, particularly with the EU Nature Restoration Regulation. Effective restoration planning requires accurate understanding of current and historical species distributions and habitat reference conditions (Schubert et al., 2015).

Denmark hosts extensive eelgrass meadows along its more than

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7000 km coastline. Its shallow, gently sloping moraine setting with numerous sheltered embayments and inlets provides ideal habitat, making Denmark home to the largest eelgrass distribution in the Nordic region (Boström et al., 2014). The actual eelgrass area extent in Denmark is not quantified but the potential distribution area has previously been estimated at approximately 2200 km² (Staehr et al., 2019), which is only one third of the historic area, estimated at approximately 6700 km² in 1900 (Petersen, 1913), although the confidence of this historical estimate is difficult to assess. The initial driver of loss was the eelgrass wasting disease, which decimated eelgrass in Denmark as well as in the broader north-Atlantic region by 80-90% in the early 1930s (Rasmussen, 1977). Although natural recovery took place over the following decades, eutrophication combined with physical disturbances from trawling, heatwaves in shallow quiescent waters, and other pressures are still limiting recovery Danish eelgrass meadows despite several action plans for the marine environment (Krause-Jensen et al., 2021). While long-term monitoring programs have delivered transect-based observations of eelgrass cover and depth range, spatially comprehensive distribution maps are needed to identify current areal extent and support management decisions across coastal water bodies regarding eelgrass protection and restoration and wider marine spatial planning. Mapping is also particularly critical for countries where eelgrass distribution indicators serve as intercalibrated Water Framework Directive biological quality elements; which is the case for eelgrass depth limits across Denmark, Sweden and Germany (Commission, 2024).

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) have emerged as powerful tools for predicting species distributions under various environmental conditions and are increasingly recognized for marine conservation planning (Bertelli et al., 2022; Norberg et al., 2019). Although attempts have been made to map the national distribution of eelgrass in Denmark

(Staehr et al., 2019), a consistent high-resolution modelling framework applicable across all Danish coastal water bodies is needed to support comparable ecological status assessments and enable efficient application to both data-rich and data-sparse areas. Most existing SDMs generate only “probability of occurrence” maps, falling short of predicting areal extent with high confidence as well as associated metrics such as depth limits that directly inform water quality assessment and restoration target-setting (Bertelli et al., 2022). Hence, most existing SDMs do not quantify specific ecological variables, such as the maximum depth limit for the main distribution of eelgrass (Z_{max} , typically defined as the maximum depth of 10% cover), which, as mentioned above, is a key bioindicator under the EU WFD for some EU member states used to determine ecological status and restoration targets (Krause-Jensen and Rasmussen, 2009; Timmermann et al., 2020). Furthermore, most mapping studies, including Danish ones, are localized in scope (Canal-Vergés et al., 2016; Kuusemäe et al., 2016) or limited by the absence of systematic biological survey data, as also highlighted by Bertelli et al. (2022).

This study addresses these critical gaps by utilizing extensive data from the Danish Monitoring Program (NOVANA, 2011–2022) to construct a high-resolution (50 × 50 m), nationwide SDM for eelgrass, *Z. marina*. By incorporating key environmental variables and estimating maximum depth limits (Z_{max}), this represents a unique, data-driven approach to identifying ecological thresholds beyond traditional probability mapping, providing valuable insights for WFD applications and restoration planning.

Fig. 1. Study area and eelgrass monitoring locations in Denmark. The grey shaded areas represent the model extent, which represents depth up to 10m. Dots indicate eelgrass transect locations from the Danish NOVANA monitoring program, with black dots representing areas with <10 % eelgrass cover and green ≥10 % cover.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area

The study area covers all Danish coastal waters in both the Baltic and the North Atlantic region including the Kattegat, the Danish Straits and the Wadden Sea as well as estuaries, lagoons, bays and open stretches along the coastline (Fig. 1). In total, more than 7000 km of coastline fringed by shallow waters is used in this study. More detailed description of the characteristic of Danish marine waters is provided by Stæhr et al. (2019).

2.2. Monitoring data

Eelgrass transect data for the years 2011–2022 were obtained from the Danish National Monitoring and Assessment Programme for the Aquatic and Terrestrial Environment (NOVANA). Eelgrass data collection is undertaken by local authorities according to detailed national guidelines (Høgslund et al., 2013).

The monitoring program employs T-shaped transects from shore to eelgrass depth limits. Eelgrass percent cover gets recorded at observation points using video sledge surveys (every 5 seconds, ~2m-wide × 5-10m segments) or SCUBA diver surveys (systematic points at 15-20m intervals, each ~2m × 5m). Surveys are conducted annually between June 1 and September 30, when eelgrass reaches maximum annual distribution. Quality assurance includes multi-level data validation (automated checks and manual supervisory review) in the database system, regular inter-observer calibration meetings to standardize cover estimations and species identification, and equipment verification protocols as detailed by Høgslund et al. (2013).

The dataset comprised 37,497 individual observations of *Z. marina* from 761 transects (2011-2022, mean 385 transects/year). Each observation records eelgrass cover as a percentage of the soft substrate at a specific geographic location and depth. To integrate the point observations with environmental variables for SDM, we aggregated data onto a consistent 50 × 50m spatial grid matching the bathymetry raster (section 2.3).

Each observation was assigned to its corresponding grid cell, and coverage percentages were averaged to create a single representative value per cell. This aggregation follows established spatial modelling practices (Downie et al., 2013; Vallea et al., 2012) and helps minimize spatial autocorrelation in ecological modelling (Downie et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2023).

Following aggregation, the mean coverage values per cell were binarized into presence-absence classes using a 10% coverage threshold. This threshold corresponds to Denmark's definition of Z_{max} , i.e. the maximum depth where eelgrass cover reaches 10% along transects, which serves as the biological quality element for assessing coastal ecological status under WFD (Miljøministeriet, 2023). Within the NOVANA monitoring program, Z_{max} is operationally assessed with 7–10 transects per water body (Bruhn et al., 2021). This approach yielded 23,257 absence records and 14,240 presence records used in the modelling.

2.3. Bathymetry

Bathymetry data was obtained from the Danish bathymetry model with mean depths at 50 × 50 m resolution (Geodatastyrelsen, 2024). The Danish dataset covers areas within the entire Danish EEZ. The dataset provides depth information essential for calculating light availability at depth and defining the spatial extent of shallow coastal habitats where eelgrass typically occurs. The bathymetric grid served as the reference grid for all spatial analyses, ensuring consistent spatial alignment between biological observations and environmental variables.

2.4. Environmental variables

Environmental variables were chosen a priori according to established knowledge of eelgrass habitat requirements in Danish water. This knowledge was compiled through previous Danish modelling studies, beginning with, further refined by Timmermann et al. (2021) and Stæhr et al. (2024), and also complemented by variables included in previously published SDMs of macrophytes (Bertelli et al., 2022).

The final environmental variables included in our study were: light availability at the seabed (I_z , %), bottom temperature (95th percentile, T95), sediment type, and Maximum Exposure Index (MEI). The MEI represents a newly developed parameter in the current study, replacing the Exposure Index used in our previous work (described in section 2.4.3). Additionally, sediment type data were not used as a direct predictor but were applied as a spatial mask after model execution to restrict predictions to suitable substrate types (section 2.4.4).

To ensure model stability and interpretability, we assessed multicollinearity among the three continuous environmental predictors using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis in Jupyter Python (Version 7.2.2). VIF quantifies how much the variance of a regression coefficient is inflated due to collinearity with other predictors. All three predictors exhibited low VIF values (T95: 4.83, I_z : 3.13, MEI: 2.62), well below the commonly accepted threshold of 5 (James et al., 2022), indicating minimal multicollinearity. This served as a preprocessing step to ensure that the selected variables were appropriately independent and not overly redundant. The distributions of environmental variables are presented in the Supplementary Material (Fig. S1). All predictor layers were projected onto the bathymetric reference grid at 50 × 50 m resolution (section 2.3) using the terra package (v. 1.8-15) in R (v. R-4.2.1).

2.4.1. Light at sea bottom (%) under current condition

For the estimation of light availability at sea bottom (I_z), data on the diffuse light attenuation coefficient for photosynthetically active radiation between 400 and 700 nm (K_d (m^{-1})) were obtained from the Danish NOVANA monitoring program for the period 2011-2022 at ~218 monitoring stations sampled biweekly to monthly, predominantly during June-November. K_d measurements follow standardized NOVANA protocols (Markager and Fossing, 2014) using dual quantum PAR sensors (400-700 nm, measuring photon flux density in $\mu Em^{-2}s^{-1}$): a surface reference sensor and an underwater sensor mounted on a CTD frame. This setup measured vertical light profiles at 0.2 m depth intervals from surface to bottom (or to <1% surface light intensity), with K_d calculated from linear regression of ln-transformed relative light intensity against depth. Quality assurance procedures include sensor cleaning and calibration following manufacturer specifications, manual review of ln-transformed light profiles by experienced staff to identify the linear depth interval, and exclusion of measurements affected by surface wave effects, ship shading, or bottom resuspension (Markager and Fossing, 2014).

The K_d data layer was interpolated with an advanced Ordinary Kriging procedure tailored for complex coastlines (Holbach et al., 2025). This method uses in-water cost-distances to estimate K_d values across the study area based on PAR-profile measurements at NOVANA monitoring stations. To estimate I_z (%), we applied the Beer-Lambert Law to measured light attenuation coefficients. Light availability at sea bottom was calculated using the following equation:

$$I_z(\%) = e^{-K_d \cdot z} \times 100 \quad \text{eq (1)}$$

where:

K_d is the light attenuation coefficient (m^{-1})

z is the water depth (m), derived from the bathymetric data layer.

I_z (%) represents the percentage of surface light reaching the seafloor at given water depths (z).

This metric is ecologically relevant for eelgrass, which requires a minimum of approximately 11% of surface irradiance at the seafloor to maintain positive growth under favourable conditions (light compensation point (Dennison, 1987; Duarte, 1991));, though the threshold can increase substantially to 30-50% under stress factors such as elevated temperatures or physical disturbance (Krause-Jensen et al., 2021). By quantifying light availability at the seabed, this variable helps identify areas where light conditions may limit eelgrass establishment or persistence.

2.4.2. Water temperature

Water temperature depth-profiles were obtained from the NOVANA monitoring programme for the period 2011-2022. For each monitoring station and for both depth-intervals (0-5 and 5-10 m), we estimated T_{95} , defined as the 95th percentile of observed temperatures representing near maximum summer conditions. For each depth interval we calculated an interpolated T_{95} layer by means of the above-mentioned Ordinary Kriging procedure tailored for complex coastlines (Holbach et al., 2025a). To estimate sea bottom T_{95} , we integrated these two depth-stratified layers (0-5m and 5-10m) based on corresponding local bathymetry for each grid cell as selection criterion.

We used T_{95} as one of the predictor variables, based on its performance as shown in (Timmermann et al., 2021) compared to the mean temperature used in previous publication (Stæhr et al., 2019), but also following the recommendation from a recent study to incorporate metrics beyond mean temperature, such as extreme temperatures, to fully characterize environmental impacts on eelgrass (*Z. marina*) productivity and resilience (Krumhansl et al., 2021). Stæhr et al. (2019) also highlighted that mean summer temperatures might underestimate the actual stress experienced by eelgrass, as high mean temperatures are related to much higher maximum temperatures, which can extend beyond the eelgrass optimum of 20 °C (Stæhr et al., 2019; Krause-Jensen et al., 2021); hence, explicitly recommending the use of extreme temperatures above optimum to better capture these critical thermal impacts. Eelgrass is particularly sensitive to episodic high-temperature exposures, which can exceed physiological capabilities and trigger stress responses such as reduced photosynthetic efficiency, increased respiration, and tissue degradation (Pulido and Borum, 2010).

2.4.3. Maximum Exposure Index (MEI)

We developed a Maximum Exposure Index (MEI) to capture peak wave exposure at eelgrass sites. The commonly used Relative exposure index (REI) is an index for the average wave exposure at a specific site. While it serves as a valuable predictor, Krause-Jensen et al. (2003) found it insufficient to explain eelgrass absence at moderately exposed sites with adequate light, suggesting that extreme wind events play a critical role. This aligns with Short and Wyllie-Echeverria (1996), who documented that storm-driven waves cause leaf breakage, plant uprooting, reduced light availability through sediment resuspension, and ultimately altered seagrass distribution. The MEI addresses this limitation by quantifying maximum potential wave energy rather than average conditions, providing a more ecologically relevant parameter for modelling *Z. marina* habitat. Eelgrass is highly sensitive to wave disturbance, which can uproot plants, mobilize sediments, and fragment meadows (Fonseca and Bell, 1998; Fonseca et al., 1983), making wave exposure a critical determinant of seagrass landscape structure and persistence (Fonseca and Bell, 1998). The species' dependence on sheltered conditions for establishment and long-term persistence has been well-documented across multiple geographic regions (Fonseca and Bell, 1998; Stæhr et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2023). For each grid cell, MEI was calculated as follows:

$$MEI = \max(V(i) \cdot F(i)) \quad (\text{eq 2})$$

with maximum wind speeds (V , in $m s^{-1}$) and effective fetch (F , in m) in eight compass directions (i).

Wind data were obtained from the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), measured at 10 m height with a spatial resolution of $1.67 \text{ min} \times 1.00 \text{ min}$, covering the period from 2011 to 2022 at hourly intervals. From the daily values the maximum of the daily mean wind speeds for each of the eight effective fetch directions was calculated. The effective fetch (F) was calculated using a vector-based approach, with points placed on a 100 m grid near the coastline and at increasing distances offshore. From each point, 32 straight lines were projected at 11.25° intervals to the nearest coastline to estimate fetch. To reduce artifacts inherent in the vector-based method, effective fetch was computed by averaging the fetch lengths of the eight neighbouring directions, each weighted by a cosine function-giving less weight to more distant lines. The maximum fetch length for open water conditions was set to 50 km to capture realistic exposure gradients in Danish coastal waters while preventing overestimation in areas with unlimited fetch.

High MEI values indicate areas of greater exposure, which may inhibit eelgrass through reduced recruitment success, seedling mortality, failed vegetative colonization, and uprooting of established plants, while lower MEI values facilitate all life stages from initial colonization to meadow persistence.

2.4.4. Sediment condition

The GIS data layer on sediment characteristics was provided by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) and consists of seven sediment classes: gravel and coarse sand, mud and sandy mud, muddy sand, quaternary clay and silt, sand, sedimentary rock, and till/diamicton (unsorted glacial sediment). The sediment map is primarily based on data intended for a coarse target scale resolution of 1:250,000.

A binary sediment mask was applied to exclude only sedimentary rock outcrops (weight = 0), which prevent rhizome anchoring (Koch, 2001), while retaining all other sediment types as suitable (weight = 1.0). This permissive approach, in contrast to our previous conservative exclusion of fine-grained sediments (Stæhr et al., 2019), reflects evidence that eelgrass can establish across diverse substrates, including mud and clay, under favourable environmental conditions (Koch, 2001; Wicks et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2015). While the binary mask addresses substrate type (consolidated vs. unconsolidated), sediment stability is captured indirectly through MEI, as wave exposure determines both grain size distribution and sediment mobility (Fonseca and Bell, 1998). High exposure areas are characterized by coarser, more mobile sediments unsuitable for eelgrass anchoring, while sheltered areas have finer, more stable sediments. The mask was applied multiplicatively to RF probability predictions, setting values to zero only for sedimentary rock while preserving continuous probability distributions (0–1) across other substrate types.

2.5. Species distribution model

Species distribution modelling (SDM) was conducted using PyCaret (version 3.3.2) in Python to compare multiple machine learning algorithms. The dataset comprised 37,497 observations (after removing NA values), randomly partitioned into training (29,997 observations; 80%) and testing (7500 observations; 20%) sets using stratified sampling to maintain class balance. Data preprocessing included normalization of predictor variables using zscore (mean = 0 and standard deviation = 1) to ensure comparability across algorithms. The target variable was eelgrass presence/absence, derived from the 10% coverage threshold as explained in Section 2.2.

Multiple machine learning algorithms were systematically evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation, including Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Extra Trees, XGBoost, and Support Vector Machines. Each algorithm was trained on 9 folds (~27,000 observations) and validated on the remaining fold (~3000 observations), with this process repeated 10 times. The RF algorithm demonstrated superior and stable performance and was selected as the final model. Model performance was evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC,

with results reported as mean \pm standard deviation across folds. In addition to the statistical validation, the model was further validated against field transect data and through spatial prediction performance.

The final RF classifier model was configured with 300 trees, maximum depth of 20, minimum samples per split of 10, minimum samples per leaf of 5, square root feature selection, and balanced class weights. Hyperparameters were optimized to balance predictive performance with generalization capability, avoiding overfitting to ensure accurate predictions on unseen data.

2.5.1. Model validation and generalization assessment

Model generalization was evaluated using four complementary validation approaches: (1) stratified 10-fold cross-validation (internal validation, coefficient of variation <5%) (Raschka, 2018), (2) independent test set evaluation ($n = 7500$; external validation on unseen data) (Raschka, 2018; Zadrozny and Elkan, 2002), (3) train-test gap analysis (Barreñada et al., 2024; Raschka, 2018), and (4) out-of-bag validation from RF's bootstrap aggregation (Breiman, 2001).

Confidence intervals (95%) were calculated using two methods: t-distribution for cross-validation metrics (appropriate for 10 independent fold estimates (Nadeau and Bengio, 1999);) and bootstrap resampling with 1000 iterations for test set metrics (Efron and Tibshirani, 1994).

Test set performance was evaluated using confusion matrices (Fig. 2C) to assess sensitivity/recall (true presences correctly identified), specificity (true absences correctly identified), precision (reliability of presence predictions), and F1-score (harmonic mean of precision and recall). We evaluated potential data leakage, which occurs when information from the test dataset inadvertently influences model training and leads to inflated performance estimates that do not reflect true predictive ability on independent data. Data leakage and overfitting were assessed via diagnostic criteria: comparison of training and test set performance to evaluate generalization gap, examination of cross-validation standard deviation (SD) to assess model stability, alignment between cross-validation and independent test performance to verify consistent generalization, and statistical comparison of performance metrics using 95% confidence intervals.

2.5.2. Prediction confidence and uncertainty quantification

Prediction confidence was quantified to assess spatial reliability of model predictions following established methods for ensemble classifiers (Breiman, 2001). An ensemble model, like RF, is recognized as a powerful technique to address uncertainty, as the diversity of predictions in an ensemble provides a natural way to estimate uncertainty (Koldasbayeva et al., 2024).

Prediction confidence was quantified separately for presence and absence predictions to provide class-specific measures of spatial

reliability. For each pixel, confidence of presence was calculated as the proportion of trees in the RF ensemble voting for the presence class (range: 0.5–1, where 1 indicates maximum confidence). This metric directly reflects the degree of consensus among the 300 decision trees and provides a spatially explicit measure of prediction confidence.

To validate that this confidence metric provides meaningful reliability information, model calibration was assessed on the independent test set using two complementary approaches. First, vote-based confidence was calculated separately for absence and presence predictions and categorized into five levels (Very Low, Low, Medium, High, Very High). Second, classification threshold uncertainty was computed as the proximity of the ensemble-averaged probability to the decision threshold ($u = 1 - 2|p - 0.5|$, where p is mean predicted probability across all 300 trees), ranging from 0 (high confidence, far from threshold) to 1 (high uncertainty, near 0.5 threshold) (Zadrozny and Elkan, 2002), and categorized into four levels (Low, Medium, High, Very High). The calculated probability estimate p represents the consensus among the numerous independent trees (300 in our case) built in the RF algorithm, and when many models agree (high p or low p), confidence is high. When they disagree (p is near the decision threshold, typically 0.5), uncertainty is high (Koldasbayeva et al., 2024). This metric identifies areas where small changes in environmental conditions or model parameters could alter predictions, which is particularly relevant for conservation planning in transitional habitats (Beale and Lennon, 2012; Rocchini et al., 2011).

To validate that these confidence metrics provide meaningful reliability information, model calibration was assessed on the independent test set using established calibration evaluation methods (Gneiting et al., 2007; Vaicenavicius et al., 2019). Calibration refers to the statistical consistency between the predictions and the observations (Gneiting et al., 2007; Norberg et al., 2019), and a well-calibrated model predicts probabilities that accurately reflect the actual likelihood of outcomes, ensuring that these probabilities are reliable and can be interpreted as accurate confidence levels (Koldasbayeva et al., 2024; Zadrozny and Elkan, 2002). Vote-based confidence and boundary-based uncertainty were categorized into discrete strata (five levels for confidence: Very Low to Very High; four levels for uncertainty: Low to Very High), and prediction accuracy was calculated within each stratum (Fig. 3).

2.5.3. Model interpretability

Model interpretability was assessed through Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) analysis, using the established method by Apley and Zhu (2020). ALE quantifies the marginal effect of individual predictors on the response variable, which is eelgrass presence probability in our case, while accounting for feature correlations. Analysing the relative importance of inherently interlinked parameters, such as light and

Fig. 2. Comprehensive model validation showing cross-validation and independent test performance. (A) Performance metrics comparison between 10-fold cross-validation (blue) and independent test set (red). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals (CV: t-distribution; Test: bootstrap with 1000 iterations). (B) Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for both validation approaches, demonstrating consistent discrimination ability. Filled circles indicate operating points at 0.5 probability threshold. Dashed diagonal line represents random classifier performance. (C) Confusion matrix for independent test set with raw counts and percentages.

temperature in our case, is challenging (Krumhansl et al., 2021), especially when using standard permutation importance analysis due to features inherent correlations. Therefore, ALE plots were generated for key environmental variables with bootstrap confidence intervals ($n = 100$ samples) (Fig. 4A–C) to better isolate individual predictor effects. The ALE method computes local prediction differences when feature values are perturbed within their natural ranges, providing ecologically meaningful insights into species-environment relationships (Molnar, 2025). Smoothing was applied using spline interpolation to enhance visualization while preserving underlying functional relationships.

2.5.4. Spatial prediction and confidence mapping

The validated RF model with confidence metrics was applied to the full environmental raster stack covering Danish coastal waters resulting in 11,700,882 pixels. For each $50\text{m} \times 50\text{m}$ pixel with complete predictor data the model generated: (1) binary presence/absence predictions based on a 0.5 probability threshold, (2) class-specific confidence scores for presence predictions, calculated as the proportion of trees voting for presence.

Two primary spatial products were generated for visualization and analysis: a prediction raster displaying binary eelgrass presence/absence across the study area (Fig. 5A), a confidence raster showing the model's confidence in presence predictions (range: 0–1) (Fig. 5B). The confidence raster enables identification of high-certainty suitable habitat areas versus regions where presence predictions carry greater uncertainty.

2.5.5. Estimation and validation of eelgrass depth limits (Z_{max})

The deep colonization limit (Z_{max}) representing the depth of the main eelgrass distribution was estimated from SDM predictions for each water body delineated under Denmark's national WFD classification. For pixels within each water body (0–10m depth range), the RF model generated binary presence/absence predictions. Depth-probability relationships were visualized by binning predictions into 0.2m depth intervals and calculating the percentage of pixels predicted as present within each bin (minimum 3 pixels per bin).

The SDM-derived Z_{max} for each water body was defined as the 90th percentile depth among all pixels predicted as eelgrass presence (binary prediction = 1). This upper percentile approach captures the realistic deep edge of eelgrass distribution while accounting for natural variability and reducing sensitivity to outliers or erroneous predictions at extreme depths.

SDM-derived Z_{max} estimates were validated against independent observed depth limits reported for eelgrass within Denmark's third River Basin Management Plan (referred as “Observed WFD Z_{max} ” hereafter (Miljøministeriet, 2023)), where observed Z_{max} represents the maximum depth of the main eelgrass distribution defined by a minimum coverage threshold of 10%. For each water body with available Observed WFD Z_{max} data, depth-probability curves were visualized alongside vertical reference lines indicating both Observed WFD Z_{max} and SDM-predicted Z_{max} .

Agreement between Observed WFD Z_{max} and SDM-predicted Z_{max} was quantified using Orthogonal Distance Regression (ODR), also termed Model II regression. Unlike ordinary least squares regression, which minimizes only vertical distances, ODR minimizes the perpendicular (orthogonal) distance from each point to the regression line, providing unbiased parameter estimates when both variables contain measurement error. Model performance was evaluated using: (1) Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and coefficient of determination (R^2) to quantify linear relationship strength, (2) ODR slope to assess systematic bias (ideal = 1.0 indicates no over-/underestimation), and (3) ODR intercept to identify constant offset (ideal = 0.0 indicates no systematic depth shift). A 1:1 reference line was included to visualize perfect agreement. The analysis included 85 water bodies with both Observed WFD Z_{max} measurements and valid SDM predictions.

3. Results

3.1. Model performance and generalization

3.1.1. Cross-validation performance and stability

Ten-fold stratified cross-validation demonstrated robust and stable model performance across data partitions. The model achieved a mean accuracy of 79.8% (95% CI: 79.4–80.2%, SD = 0.55%) with the Area Under the ROC Curve was 0.878 (95% CI: 0.871–0.883), indicating strong discriminative ability between eelgrass presence and absence (Fig. 2A).

Model stability was very high, with a coefficient of variation below 1% for both accuracy (0.69%) and AUC (0.73%), well under the 5% benchmark for reliable ecological models. Fold-to-fold variation was minimal: accuracy ranged from 1.6 percentage points (78.99–80.59%) and F1-score varied 2.1 percentage points across folds, confirming robustness to different data partitions.

3.1.2. Independent test set performance

On the held-out test set ($n = 7500$), the model achieved an accuracy of 80.3% (95% CI: 79.4–81.2%), precision of 72.0% (95% CI: 70.4–73.6%), recall of 78.3% (95% CI: 76.8–79.8%), F1-score of 75.0% (95% CI: 73.8–76.3%), and specificity of 81.5% (95% CI: 80.4–82.6%) (Fig. 2A). The model demonstrated good discrimination ability with an area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.878 on the independent test set, nearly identical to the cross-validation AUC of 0.878, confirming robust generalization without overfitting (Fig. 2B). This high AUC indicates that the model correctly ranks 87.8% of randomly selected presence-absence pairs, substantially outperforming random classification (AUC = 0.5). The overlapping ROC curves between cross-validation and test data (Fig. 2B) demonstrate consistent discrimination performance across all probability thresholds, validating the model's reliability for spatial prediction applications. Bootstrap confidence intervals (1000 iterations) were narrow across all metrics, with accuracy varying by only 1.80 percentage points, confirming statistical robustness.

3.1.3. Validation of generalization

Cross-validation and test set performance showed strong alignment, providing multiple lines of evidence for robust generalization without data leakage. Test accuracy fell within the cross-validation 95% confidence interval (CV: 79.8% [79.4–80.2%] vs. Test: 80.3% [79.4–81.2%]), with near-identical performance (0.5 percentage point difference) (Fig. 2A). Confidence intervals overlapped across all metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score), confirming consistent predictive performance across validation approaches.

The training-test accuracy gap of 9.6% indicated appropriate learning capacity on both training and unseen data without overfitting. Out-of-bag validation yielded 79.9% accuracy, independently corroborating cross-validation and test results. Together, these complementary validation approaches, narrow fold-to-fold variation (CV < 1%), aligned CV-test performance (difference < 0.5%), minimal train-test gap (~10%), and concordant OOB estimates, provide strong evidence that the model generalizes reliably to unseen coastal areas and is suitable for spatial prediction applications.

3.1.4. Prediction confidence and calibration

Analysis of vote-based confidence revealed that the model assigns slightly higher confidence to predicted absences (mean = 0.78) compared to presences (mean = 0.73) (Fig. 3A). Prediction uncertainty showed the opposite pattern, with absences showing lower mean uncertainty (0.43) compared to presences (0.54), though both classes showed substantial overlap in their distributions (Fig. 3B). Critically, the model demonstrated strong calibration: accuracy increased systematically with vote confidence, ranging from 57.8% at very low confidence to 97.2% at very high confidence (Fig. 3C). Similarly, accuracy declined with increasing uncertainty, from 95.3% at low uncertainty to 61.5% at

Fig. 3. Prediction confidence and uncertainty analysis. (A) Distribution of vote-based confidence scores by predicted class. Dashed lines indicate mean confidence for absences (blue) and presences (green). (B) Distribution of prediction uncertainty by predicted class. (C) Model calibration showing accuracy increases with vote confidence, demonstrating well-calibrated predictions. (D) Model calibration by uncertainty level, with accuracy declining at higher uncertainty thresholds. Sample sizes shown as insets in bars.

very high uncertainty (Fig. 3D). Using an 80% confidence threshold retains 1532 high-confidence predictions with 89.1% accuracy, while the low uncertainty category (<0.22) contains 2492 predictions with 95.3% accuracy. This calibration enables identification of spatially explicit areas where predictions are most reliable for management applications.

3.2. Environmental drivers of eelgrass

Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) plots revealed distinct non-linear relationships between environmental predictors and eelgrass presence probability (Fig. 4).

Light availability exhibited the expected saturating photosynthetic response curve, with optimal suitability between 20 and 75% surface irradiance (Fig. 4A). Predicted suitability declined sharply below 20% irradiance, indicating light limitation for growth and survival. Suitability also decreased above 75% irradiance, potentially reflecting photoinhibition, though high light conditions often co-occur with elevated temperatures and increased wave exposure, confounding direct interpretation.

Wave exposure showed a clear negative relationship with habitat suitability (Fig. 4B). Eelgrass probability declined steeply with increasing Maximum Exposure Index (MEI), confirming the species' preference for sheltered to moderately exposed locations and sensitivity to high wave energy environments that cause physical disturbance.

Temperature (T95) displayed a unimodal response with apparent thermal optima between 19 and 21.5 °C (Fig. 4C). However, substantial uncertainty at temperature extremes, particularly below 17 °C and above 22 °C, which reflects limited observations in these ranges and warrants cautious interpretation of threshold effects.

3.3. Spatial distribution and confidence assessment

The RF model predicted eelgrass distribution totalling ~ 2000 km² (precisely 1989 km²) across Danish waters, revealing distinct spatial patterns in eelgrass distribution (Fig. 5A). Eelgrass meadows are

predicted primarily in shallow, sheltered coastal environments, with the most extensive coverage concentrated in southern Denmark. Notable areas of predicted presence include waters surrounding southern Funen and Zealand, where suitable depth and wave protection create favourable habitat conditions. Significant eelgrass populations are also predicted within estuaries, particularly Limfjorden, where enclosed, shallow environments provide optimal growing conditions for *Z. marina*. An additional large distribution area is in Øresund, the sound connecting Denmark and Sweden.

In contrast, the model predicts near-complete absence along Denmark's western North Sea-facing coastline, consistent with ecological expectations given the high wave exposure in this region. This stark contrast between sheltered eastern and southern waters versus the exposed western coast underscores the critical importance of wave protection for eelgrass establishment and persistence.

Prediction confidence varied spatially (Fig. 5B), with the model showing high confidence in predicting eelgrass presence at many established meadow locations within southern estuaries, including waters surrounding southern Funen, Zealand, and Limfjorden, validating its ability to identify core habitat. Of the 795,745 pixels classified as presence (1989 km²), 40.8% (812 km²) showed very high confidence (confidence ≥ 0.70), concentrated in established meadow locations within sheltered estuaries. Moderate to high confidence (0.60–0.70) characterized 28.3% (563 km²) of predictions, while 30.9% (614 km²) showed moderate confidence (0.50–0.60).

3.4. Model assessment at local scale

The spatial validation reveals strong agreement between RF model predictions and field observations across all eight water bodies (WB) (Fig. 6A–H). These validation sites encompass diverse coastal environments, including inner estuaries, outer estuaries, and open coastal habitats, ensuring comprehensive assessment of model performance across the full range of eelgrass-suitable environments.

The model demonstrates high predictive accuracy, with transect data consistently aligning with predicted eelgrass presence areas across all

Fig. 4. Accumulated Local Effects (ALE) plots showing non-linear relationships between eelgrass habitat suitability and environmental predictors: (A) Light availability at bottom depth (%), (B) Maximum Exposure Index (MEI), and (C) Temperature 95th percentile (T95).

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution and prediction confidence of eelgrass in Danish waters. (A) Predicted eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) presence (green) and absence (grey). (B) Prediction confidence map for areas classified as suitable habitat, showing confidence ranging from <0.5 (low confidence), 0.50 (moderate confidence) to >0.8 (very high confidence).

eight WB. Notably, transect points showing eelgrass presence in the range of 10-100% (green) consistently fall within predicted suitable habitat areas (dark green), while absence points representing 0-10% mean coverage (black) align with predicted unsuitable areas (grey). The model successfully captures the spatial heterogeneity and patchy distribution of eelgrass habitat, accurately delineating habitat boundaries

at a fine spatial scale.

3.5. Depth limits for the main distribution of eelgrass

The RF model effectively captured depth-related patterns of eelgrass distribution across Danish coastal waters. Analysis of eelgrass presence

Fig. 6. Model validation across eight Danish water bodies (WB) comparing RF predictions with mean transect survey data (2011-2022). Dark green areas indicate predicted eelgrass presence; grey areas show predicted absence. Black points = mean eelgrass coverage in transects (<10%), green points = eelgrass presence in transects (>10% coverage). Insets show locations within Denmark.

probability across depth gradients revealed that eelgrass occurrence remained relatively high (40-55%) in shallow waters (0-6 m), declining progressively with increasing depth. The probability of eelgrass presence dropped below the 10% threshold in the 6-8 m depth range (Figure shown in Supplementary Material; S2), indicating the practical depth limit for eelgrass distribution in the study area. Model predictions closely aligned with observed probability patterns across all depth bins (correlation = 0.995), demonstrating the model's ability to accurately capture depth-dependent distribution patterns.

In addition, model predictions demonstrated strong agreement with observed Zmax values reported under the WFD. Eelgrass presence probability profiles from eight representative water bodies (Fig. 7, panels A-H) reveal characteristic depth-dependent declines in habitat suitability. Shallow depth limits occurred at sheltered estuaries with high light attenuation, such as Roskilde Fjord (WB #2, observed: 2.95 m, predicted: 2.67 m) and Nibe Bredning (WB #235, observed: 2.44 m, predicted: 2.44m). In contrast, deeper depth limits (5-7 m) occurred in clearer, more open waters, including Nordlige Øresund (WB #6,

Fig. 7. Depth-dependent eelgrass presence probability in eight representative Danish water bodies. Curves show modelled probability of eelgrass presence declining with depth (green circles). Green vertical lines indicate SDM-predicted depth limits, and red lines indicate observed WFD Zmax values. Sites represent diverse coastal environments including inner estuaries (A, H), outer estuaries and embayments (C, D, E, G), and open coasts (B, F).

observed: 6.35 m, predicted: 5.72 m) and Køge Bugt (WB #201, observed: 6.78 m, predicted: 5.99 m). The model-predicted depth limits, defined where eelgrass presence probability falls below 10%, closely aligned with Observed WFD Zmax values across this diverse range of coastal environments, confirming the model's ability to capture site-specific depth distributions.

3.5.1. Quantitative validation against Water Framework Directive depth limits

Quantitative validation across 85 water bodies demonstrated robust model performance in predicting eelgrass depth limits (Fig. 8). Predicted Zmax showed strong correlation with Zmax values reported to WFD for each water body delineated under Denmark's national WFD classification ($r = 0.779$, $R^2 = 0.607$, $p < 0.001$). ODR, accounting for measurement uncertainty in both variables, yielded near-unity slope (0.99) and near-zero intercept (0.08 m), confirming minimal systematic bias across the full depth range (0.5–8.0 m). Model accuracy remained

consistent across shallow (<3 m), intermediate (3–6 m), and deep (>6 m) sites, validating its mechanistic capture of environmental controls on depth distribution.

4. Discussion

This study provides a robust SDM for *Zostera marina* that improves quantification of eelgrass distribution patterns across Danish coastal waters and offers an improved framework for conservation and restoration planning for a key habitat.

The nationwide coverage estimates of ~2000 km² eelgrass across Danish shallow waters, with possibility to estimate the depth limit (Zmax) for the main distribution of eelgrass, represent the first comprehensive SDM based assessment of Zmax in Danish waters. This work provides essential baseline information highlighting areas important for eelgrass for implementing national and international conservation targets, particularly those outlined in the EU Nature Restoration

Fig. 8. Validation of model-predicted eelgrass depth limits against field observations Z_{\max} values. Each point represents one water body ($n = 84$). The red line shows orthogonal distance regression (ODR), which accounts for uncertainty in both variables. The grey dashed line represents perfect 1:1 agreement. Strong correlation ($r = 0.779$, $R^2 = 0.607$) and near-unity slope (0.99) indicate accurate, unbiased depth limit predictions across the full depth range.

Regulation and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

4.1. Model performance

This SDM addresses critical gaps in eelgrass modelling by delivering quantitative distribution maps with ecological thresholds and confidence metrics essential for management applications, moving beyond traditional habitat suitability mapping approaches. Despite recent advances in seagrass distribution mapping, the studies have either focused only on intertidal zones (Davies et al., 2026) or generated “probability of occurrence” maps without ecological thresholds or associated confidence metrics (Beca-Carretero et al., 2020, 2024; Davies et al., 2026; Robinson et al., 2017; Staehr et al., 2019; Vallea et al., 2012). Our model advances current knowledge by providing: (1) high-confidence, high-resolution maps of current eelgrass distributions with quantified areal extent ($\sim 2000 \text{ km}^2$), matching previous estimates of $\sim 2200 \text{ km}^2$ (Staehr et al., 2019) and (2) predicted depth limits (Z_{\max}) that closely aligned with WFD field observations ($r = 0.779$). This integration of spatial prediction with validated ecological thresholds represents a significant advancement for operational management.

Multiple lines of evidence support the model's biological realism and predictive reliability. Strong statistical performance (80.3% accuracy, $\text{AUC} = 0.878$) on the independent test set closely mirrors cross-validation results (79.8% accuracy, $\text{AUC} = 0.878$), with a negligible AUC gap and overlapping confidence intervals across all metrics. This consistency across validation approaches confirms robust generalization and absence of overfitting. As highlighted by Barreñada et al. (2024), large discrepancies between training and test metrics are a key indicator of overfitting, even in ensemble models like Random Forests. The near-identical AUC values and minimal fold-to-fold variation ($< 1\%$) in our model, thus provide strong empirical support for its reliability and ecological validity (Valle et al., 2013). Furthermore, the close spatial agreement between predictions and transect monitoring data across diverse water bodies, demonstrates that the model successfully captures

fundamental environmental drivers of eelgrass distribution. Critically, the stratified confidence analysis revealed monotonic relationships: accuracy increased systematically with vote confidence (57.8% to 97.2%) and decreased predictably with uncertainty. This calibration, validates confidence metrics as reliable indicators of spatial prediction reliability (Zadrozny and Elkan, 2002; Niculescu-Mizil and Caruana, 2005), enabling managers to identify where predictions are most trustworthy for conservation decisions (Norberg et al., 2019).

ALE analysis revealed light availability at depth as the dominant predictor of eelgrass distribution, followed by wave exposure (MEI) and temperature (T95). This hierarchy reflects well-established physiological constraints: Eelgrass requires sufficient photosynthetically active radiation to maintain positive carbon balance (Duarte, 1991), with light attenuation by turbidity typically limiting depth distribution in coastal Danish waters (Nielsen et al., 2002). While natural environmental collinearity complicates precise attribution (Dormann et al., 2013), these predictors act as interlinked drivers (Krumhansl et al., 2021): light limits photosynthetic capacity, growth and survival (Banke et al., 2025), temperature modulates metabolic demands and minimum light requirements (Staehr and Borum, 2011), and exposure affects mechanical disturbance and light availability through sediment resuspension (Koch, 2001). The model's ability to capture these complex, non-linear relationships, evidenced by strong depth limit predictions, demonstrates the model's mechanistic foundation.

4.2. Depth limit prediction

Our SDM successfully predicts ecologically meaningful depth limits for eelgrass distribution, with predictions closely matching observed WFD Z_{\max} values across 85 water bodies ($r = 0.779$, slope = 0.99, intercept = 0.08 m). The model identifies an overall depth threshold of approximately 6–8 m across Danish coastal waters, consistent with current water quality conditions (Krause-Jensen and Rasmussen, 2009), while capturing site-specific variation from turbid estuarine systems (Nibe Bredning: 2.41 m predicted vs. 2.44 m observed; Roskilde Fjord: 2.62 m vs. 2.95 m) to clearer coastal waters (Køge Bugt: 5.99 m vs. 6.78 m; Nordlige Øresund: 5.73 m vs. 6.35 m).

These current depth limits represent substantial ecological degradation from pre-1930s baselines of 8.5–10.4 m along open coasts and 3.9–10.1 m in estuaries (Krause-Jensen and Rasmussen, 2009), though extreme historical depth records beyond 12 m likely reflect methodological uncertainties (Ostenfeld, 1908). Following partial recovery from the disease, eutrophication-driven reductions in water clarity, combined with epiphyte overgrowth, physical disturbance from trawling, anoxia, and altered food webs, have compressed eelgrass to much shallower depths (Krause-Jensen et al., 2003). The model's accurate prediction of current degraded-condition depth limits, while concerning from a conservation perspective, validates its utility for tracking recovery trajectories and establishing restoration targets under improved environmental conditions.

Integrating depth limit prediction within a comprehensive SDM framework represents significant methodological advancement, providing managers with actionable metrics for setting restoration targets and evaluating water quality improvements. Robust performance across 85 diverse water bodies validates applicability for scenario modeling under improved light conditions or climate change and establishing site-specific ecological targets for WFD compliance.

4.3. Management applications and conservation significance

Eelgrass depth limits (Z_{\max}) as biological quality elements are intercalibrated under the WFD for Baltic Sea and North Sea coastal water typologies shared by Denmark, Germany, and Sweden (Commission, 2024). However, the SDM's broader outputs such as presence/absence maps, areal extent, coverage patterns, and confidence predictions, have wider applicability for WFD coastal ecological status assessment across

EU Member States, as eelgrass distribution and abundance inform multiple quality elements beyond depth limits alone. Similarly, the modelling framework itself (Random Forest methodology applied to widely available environmental predictors) is transferable to other temperate coastal regions with eelgrass.

SDMs objectively translate field observations into quantitative predictions across unsurveyed areas (Bekkby et al., 2008), generating distribution maps readily interpretable and easily communicated to stakeholders and decision-makers. Our model's strong predictive capability supplemented by confidence metrics provides unprecedented support for evidence-based conservation planning and restoration prioritization.

The model enables strategic spatial prioritization of restoration investments through its comprehensive spatial coverage. The pronounced depth limit variation between sheltered estuaries (2.4–2.6 m) and open waters (5.7–6.0 m) reveals differential water quality constraints across the seascape. Shallow depth limits in turbid estuaries (e.g., Roskilde Fjord, Nibe Bredning) identify locations where water quality improvements, through nutrient reduction or sediment management, could enable substantial depth expansion of existing eelgrass populations. Deeper limits may, however, represent higher priorities for protection from physical disturbance e.g. related to bottom trawling. This differentiated management approach is particularly valuable given limited conservation budgets and the need to demonstrate measurable outcomes toward ambitious EU biodiversity restoration targets (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024).

A key advantage is predicting depth limits under altered environmental conditions, something that monitoring alone cannot provide. The model enables quantitative evaluation of different management scenarios. For example, managers can simulate how specific water quality improvements, such as a 20% reduction in light attenuation, would expand depth limits across different water body types, thereby establishing concrete targets for nutrient management programs. This is particularly relevant for Denmark's proposed Green Tripartite Agreement (Grøn Trepert) framework, which requires evidence-based coastal water restoration targets (Transition, 2024).

For Marine Spatial Planning, the model's spatially explicit predictions with associated confidence metrics enable: (1) critical habitats delineation requiring protection from physical disturbance (e.g., bottom trawling, dredging, coastal development) (Robinson et al., 2017; O'Brien et al., 2022), (2) assessment of trade-offs between conservation and competing uses in multi-use planning zones (Downie et al., 2013; Valle et al., 2013) (3) identification of suitable sites for restoration initiatives (Flindt et al., 2016; O'Brien et al., 2022; Schubert et al., 2015) and (4) evaluation of cumulative impact scenarios under proposed development plans (O'Brien et al., 2022). The continuous spatial coverage addresses a fundamental limitation of transect-based monitoring (Schubert et al., 2015), which provides precise depth limits at specific locations but limited information about spatial patterns between monitoring sites.

Importantly, the eelgrass SDM does not replace existing monitoring programs but rather enhances their value by providing spatial context, scenario modelling capability, and comprehensive coverage that complements the temporal precision and ground-truth accuracy of diver-based transect surveys (Schubert et al., 2015). This framework addresses the full spectrum of information needs for optimal adaptive coastal management: current distribution (monitoring + SDM), potential areal extent (SDM), response to management interventions (SDM scenarios), and prediction reliable (SDM confidence metrics).

4.4. Geographical scope and framework transferability

Although this study was focused on Danish marine waters, the modelling framework has broad applicability. Eelgrass is globally the most widespread seagrass species (Green and Short, 2003) making methodological advances in eelgrass SDM highly relevant internationally. Denmark, which harbors the largest eelgrass distribution in the

Nordic region (Krause-Jensen et al., 2021; Boström et al., 2014), provides an ideal study system for framework development: the extensive spatial coverage captures diverse environmental gradients (light: 5-95% surface irradiance, temperature: 5-24 °C, exposure: sheltered to very exposed) representative of temperate eelgrass habitats globally.

Furthermore, our model predicts multiple variables-presence/absence, spatial extent, coverage, and depth limits, that directly support WFD targets regarding seagrass presence and abundance across EU Member States. While the Danish-trained model is not directly transferable to other regions, the developed framework (applying Random Forest methodology with locally collected data) is broadly applicable and can be implemented in other countries. The latter requires only: (1) georeferenced presence/absence observations (from field surveys, drones, or citizen science), (2) environmental predictors (light, temperature, exposure-derivable from satellite/oceanographic data), and (3) open-source tools (Python/R).

4.5. Data refinements and future applications

While current predictor layers effectively capture primary drivers (validated by strong depth limit predictions across 85 water bodies), several refinements could enhance predictions.

Presence threshold considerations: The 10% presence threshold classifies sparse eelgrass occurrences (<10%) as absence, potentially excluding degrading or newly colonizing areas. This 10% threshold is however, useful to identify stable and functional meadows rather than temporary or highly degraded occurrences (Commission, 2024; Høgslund et al., 2013). For restoration planning, this conservative approach ensures efforts target areas capable of supporting established meadows.

Environmental predictor refinements: Light attenuation (Kd) and temperature (T95) layers from interpolated monitoring stations may limit fine-scale nearshore variability capture. Integration with novel satellite-derived products (e.g., Sentinel-3 for both Kd and sea surface temperature) could improve both spatial and temporal resolution, though operational implementation faces technical challenges, as shown for Kd retrievals in optically shallow habitats (Holbach et al., 2025). Higher-resolution sediment data including organic content and grain size would enable nuanced substrate assessment, though current MEI effectively proxies sediment stability through wave exposure-grain size relationships.

Beyond geographic transfer, the approach enables temporal applications: historical reconstruction using pre-eutrophication light conditions could generate reference distribution maps, while climate projections incorporating temperature increases, altered wind-wave regimes, and sea level rise can estimate future habitat shifts, provided conditions remain within model training bounds. Integration with real-time environmental data would enable dynamic forecasting alerting managers to habitat loss risks or restoration opportunities (Robinson et al., 2017).

4.6. Application to support Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework targets

This modelling framework can be applied to support Denmark's contributions to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, particularly Target 2 (restoration of degraded ecosystems) and Target 3 (effective conservation of 30% of coastal and marine areas by 2030) (Fu et al., 2024). The model provides the spatial foundation for identifying degraded eelgrass habitats suitable for restoration and delineating priority conservation areas-both essential for evidence-based implementation of these targets. By predicting current distribution (~2000 km²) and, through comparison, identifying areas where historical losses have occurred, the model enables strategic restoration planning that maximizes ecological recovery relative to investment. The high spatial resolution (50 m) facilitates site-specific planning aligned

with both the KM-GBF and EU Nature Restoration Law requirements. Moreover, the transferable methodology offers a replicable approach for nations developing spatial frameworks to meet international biodiversity commitments.

5. Conclusions and perspectives

This study delivers a high-performance SDM that advances eelgrass monitoring and conservation from descriptive mapping to quantitative, actionable predictions. The Random Forest SDM model achieved exceptional accuracy (80.3%) and discrimination ability ($AUC = 0.878$) predicting 2000 km² of eelgrass across Danish coastal waters, with remarkably stable performance and high confidence demonstrated through multiple independent validation approaches. Critically, the model's ability to predict distribution boundaries, evidenced by strong agreement with observed depth limits across diverse Danish water bodies, confirms it has captured fundamental environmental processes rather than mere statistical correlations. The model provides three essential capabilities for evidence-based management: (1) high-resolution spatial predictions identifying current eelgrass distribution with quantified confidence, (2) site-specific ecological threshold predictions (depth limits) that align closely with field observations, and (3) spatially explicit confidence metrics enabling managers to identify where predictions are most reliable for guiding conservation investments. This integrated approach, combining distribution mapping, threshold quantification, and uncertainty assessment, addresses critical information gaps that have limited operational application of previous seagrass SDMs. Validation results provide compelling evidence of the model's operational readiness. The close correspondence between predictions and independent transect data across water bodies spanning diverse coastal environments, combined with accurate depth limit predictions showing minimal bias (mean error <1 m), demonstrates robust performance across the full range of Danish eelgrass habitats.

The model directly supports multiple regulatory and conservation frameworks. For WFD implementation, predicted depth limits provide quantitative baselines for setting restoration targets and evaluating progress toward Good Ecological Status. For Marine Spatial Planning, high-resolution distribution maps with confidence metrics enable identification of critical habitats requiring protection and assessment of trade-offs in multi-use planning zones. For climate adaptation planning, the mechanistic foundation enables scenario modelling of habitat responses to environmental change, identifying vulnerable systems and potential climate refugia. Looking forward, the robust predictive framework potentially enables two critical applications: (1) historical reconstruction using light attenuation estimates from pre-eutrophication conditions to establish reference baselines required under the EU Nature Restoration Law, and (2) climate projection modelling incorporating temperature increases, altered wave regimes, and sea level rise to identify future habitat shifts and prioritize adaptive management strategies. The transferable methodology, utilizing widely available environmental predictors and open-source machine learning, provides a template for other nations developing spatial planning frameworks to meet Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework targets for coastal ecosystem restoration and conservation. This work demonstrates that integrating high-resolution environmental data with advanced machine learning can deliver the spatially explicit, quantitatively rigorous predictions required for 21st-century coastal management. By bridging fundamental ecology with operational application, the model transforms eelgrass conservation planning from reactive monitoring to proactive, evidence-based decision-making capable of addressing accelerating environmental change.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sanjina Upadhyay Stæhr: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology,

Project administration, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Cordula Göke:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Andreas Michael Holbach:** Data curation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Peter Anton Upadhyay Stæhr:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Dorte-Krause Jensen:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Mihailo Azhar:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Jacob Carstensen:** Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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